

Tsallis Entropy from Maximization of Entropy and the Condition of Stability

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In a previous note (1), we argued that in the Maxwell-Boltzmann (Shannon) case, one may either maximize Shannon's entropy: $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ subject to the two a priori constraints: $\sum_i p(e_i)=1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{total}$ or use reaction balance: $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and $p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_3)p(e_4)$. The first approach may be described as maximizing the probability of N trial runs and so is linked with minimal information which is often thought of as a universal statistical principle. We argued in (1), however, that if one only uses reaction balance, there is no notion of maximizing an overall probability of N trial runs. In such a case, there seems to be a different principle at work. One may write: $p(e_i) \frac{d}{dp(e_i)} F(p(e_i))=1$ ((1)) such that $F(p(e_i))= -e_i/T$, the information. This leads to $F(p(e_i)) = \ln(p(e_i))$. We argue that ((1)) is a statement of stability. Namely, if one argues that for a given set $p(e_i)$, if one has $F(p(e_i))$, then $\sum_i \{p(e_i)+\delta p(e_i)\} F(p(e_i) + \delta p(e_i)) = \sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$. This then seems to be a way to justify ((1)) not just for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, but also for the Tsallis one.

In particular, in (1) we argue that one may obtain the Tsallis $\ln_q(p(e_i))$ from the conditions: $\ln_q(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, $\ln_q(p(e_i))$ for $q=1 = \ln(p(e_i))$ and $p(e_i)^q \frac{d}{dp(e_i)} \ln_q(p(e_i)) = 1$ ((2)). We suggest that the latter condition is one of stability and hence seems justified even if one cannot associate Tsallis entropy with the maximization of the probability of N runs. We also note that these conditions govern the nonadditivity of Tsallis entropy: $S(A,B) = S(A)+S(B) + (1-q)S(A)S(B)$.

Next, we consider (2) in which the Tsallis non-additivity condition (and that of other forms of entropy) is said to follow from the notion of a conserved quantity (e.g. e_i) and the zeroth law of thermodynamics. Secondly, (2) argues that of the many entropies which one may create, Tsallis entropy has the property of being stable, namely given an observable $C(p(e_i))$, a small change in $p(e_i)$ should also mean a small change in the observable. We argue that both the conditions of (2) actually follow from the conditions ((2)).

Maxwell-Boltzmann Entropy

We noted in (1) that there seem to be two very different approaches to finding the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution and that each implies a different "fundamental principle of statistics".

In the first case, one may consider the notion of Boltzmann entropy $-k \ln(\text{number of states})$ and maximize the number of states (minimize overall information about the system) subject to constraints. The Shannon entropy maximization is essentially the same idea. Shannon's entropy follows from:

$$\ln(\text{probability } N \text{ runs}) = \ln\left\{ \prod_i p(e_i)^{N p(e_i)} \right\} \quad ((3))$$

One may then maximize this subject to the two a priori constraints:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{total} \quad ((4))$$

We argue that these ideas lead to the following “fundamental principle of statistics”:

At least in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, a statistical system tries to create the maximum probability of N trial runs or minimum information. ((5))

((5)) is often taken as a general principle which is applied in many statistical situations.

We argue, however, that a second and different “fundamental principle of statistics” may be proposed, namely one which is associated with stability, If one considers interaction balance, then:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \text{ (energy conservation) } ((6a)) \text{ and } p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4) ((6b))$$

Taking \ln of ((6b)) and equating to $-1/T$ multiplied by ((6a)) yields the MB distribution $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ ((7)).

Now, one may propose from this the following stability condition:

$$p(e_i) \frac{d}{dp(e_i)} F(p(e_i)) = 1 \rightarrow F(p(e_i)) = \ln(p(e_i)) \quad \text{and } F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T ((8)) \text{ (Here } p(e_i) \text{ is unnormalized)}$$

We note that $\ln(p(e_i))$, the information, implies additivity (which carries over to Shannon’s entropy), but also means that:

$$\sum_i \{ p(e_i) + \delta(p(e_i)) \} F(p(e_i) + \delta(p(e_i))) = \sum_i p(e_i) F(e_i) ((9))$$

because: $\sum_i \delta(p(e_i)) = 0$ and $\sum_i e_i \delta(p(e_i)) = 0$ from the two constraints ((4)).

Thus, ((8)) allows for a different way of looking at a statistical equilibrium.

Application to the Tsallis Case

In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case there were two alternative proposals for a “fundamental statistical principle”, but in the Tsallis case, the first option is no longer present. In the Tsallis case, the a priori constraints are:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q = E_{\text{total}} ((10))$$

There is no Shannon’s entropy created from $p(e_i)$ power q and so one must consider ((8)) with

$$p(e_i) \frac{d}{dp(e_i)} F(p(e_i)) = 1 \rightarrow p(e_i)^q \frac{d}{dp(e_i)} F(p(e_i)) \quad \text{and} \quad F(p(e_i)) = -e/T$$

and $q=1$ yielding $F(p(e_i)) = \ln(p(e_i))$ ((11))

This then leads to the information: $\ln_q(p(e_i)) = \{ p(e_i)^{1-q} - 1 \} / \{ 1-q \}$ ((12))

Using $\sum_i p(e_i)^q \ln_q(p(e_i))$ one has Tsallis entropy: $-\{ 1 - \sum_i p(e_i)^q \} / \{ 1-q \}$ ((13))

We note that the nonadditivity property of Tsallis entropy (given in (2) and elsewhere) is:

$$S(A,B) = S(A) + S(B) + (1-q) S(A)S(B) \quad ((14))$$

$$\text{Here } S(A,B) = -\{ 1 - \sum_{i,j} \{ p_A(e_i) p_B(e_j) \}^q \} / (1-q) \quad ((15))$$

We argue that this additivity property already follows from $\ln_q(p(e_i))$ just as $S(AB) = S(A) + S(B)$ for Shannon's entropy follows from $\ln(p(e_i))$.

The key point, however, is that the stability condition allows for one use ((11)) to find the form $\ln_q(p(e_i))$. In particular:

$$\sum_i \{ p(e_i) + \delta(p(e_i)) \}^q F(p(e_i) + \delta(p(e_i))) =$$

$$\sum_i p(e_i)^q F(p(e_i)) - e_i/T q \delta(p(e_i)) p(e_i)^{q-1} + p(e_i)^q dF/dp(e_i) \delta(p(e_i))$$

$$\text{Now } \sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q = E_{\text{total}} \rightarrow \sum_i e_i q p(e_i)^{q-1} = 0 \quad \text{and}$$

using $p(e_i)^q dF/dp(e_i) = 1$ one has $\sum_i \delta(p(e_i)) = 0$ because $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$. (Note: the equations which = 0 could be multiplied by a normalization constant, so as in the MB case, there is no issue with $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ being linked to an unnormalized probability.

As a result, it is the notion of stability which justifies the use of ((11)) in the maximization process of Tsallis entropy subject to constraints and defines both $\ln_q(p(e_i))$ and \exp_q and hence Tsallis entropy.

Non-Additivity and Stability from a Different Viewpoint

We note that the features of nonadditivity of Tsallis entropy and stability are described in (2) in a very different manner. We argued that the nonadditivity feature follows from the stability condition ((11)) for $\ln_q(p(e_i))$. Thus, nonadditivity and the stability of Tsallis entropy go hand in hand.

Without reproducing the full work of (2), we note that (2) considers the nonadditivity condition for general entropies: $S(A,B)$ as yielding $S(A) + S(B) + f(q) S(A) S(B)$ ((12)) if one uses the notion of a conserved quantity and the zeroth law of thermodynamics. In other words, (2) argues that ((12)) applies for many general forms of entropy one may propose and that this is a direct consequence of the zeroth law of thermodynamics.

The second key argument of (2) is that Tsallis entropy is stable, whereas many other entropy forms are not. The definition of stability in (2) is that given a measurable property $C(p(e_i))$, if one changes $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + \delta p(e_i)$, C should only change infinitesimally. Thus, (2) argues that:

$$| p(e_i) + \delta p(e_i) - p(e_i) | \leq \delta \text{ means that } | C(p(e_i) + \delta p(e_i)) - C(p(e_i)) | < \text{infinitesimal value} \quad ((13))$$

Thus, we suggest that the two main conclusions of (2) are incorporated in the approach of ((11)) which we use, but that these two are both linked to the maximization of entropy subject to a priori constraints.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that there are two ways to interpret the derivation of the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. The first is to consider maximizing entropy (which is considered to be a measure of the probability (lack of information) in a system) subject to a priori constraints. The second is to argue for a stability condition: $\sum_i \{p(e_i) + \delta p(e_i)\} \ln(p(e_i) + \delta p(e_i)) = \sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$. This stability condition is equivalent to $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ (hence an unnormalized probability) and $p(e_i) d/dp(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) = 1$.

In the MB case, one may choose one viewpoint or the other, but this is not the case for the Tsallis scenario. There, there is no maximization of total number of states or probability of N trial runs. Instead, one may use the stability condition with $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ and $p(e_i)$ power q $d/dp(e_i) F(p(e_i)) = 1$. This leads to $F(p(e_i)) = \ln_q(p(e_i))$ with the imposed condition that $\ln_q(p(e_i))$ for $q=1 = \ln(p(e_i))$. Thus, we suggest that the stability condition is the one chosen for the Tsallis entropy which is: $-\sum_i p(e_i)^q \ln_q(p(e_i))$. We note that the nonadditivity condition of Tsallis entropy as well as the stability condition both follow from ((11)).

In (2), it is argued that one may create a generalized equation: $S(A,B) = S(A) + S(B) + f(q) S(A)S(B)$ for various entropic forms by using the zeroth law of thermodynamics. It is then argued, using a separate argument, which differs from ((11) which we present here, that for $| p(e_i) + \delta p(e_i) - p(e_i) | \leq \delta$, one should have: $| C(p(e_i) + \delta p(e_i)) - C(p(e_i)) | < \text{infinitesimal}$. Here $C(p(e_i))$ is a physical observable. It is argued that general entropies do not necessarily satisfy this stability condition, but that Tsallis entropy does.

References

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